

New Water Culture Questionnaire - Bogotá

INSTRUCTIONS:

Please note that this questionnaire is completely anonymous. We are interested in questions related to the use, management and saving of water. Please mark with an X the degree of agreement with the following statements. There are no right or wrong answers.

AGE: __ **GENDER:** Male Female Prefer not to say **LOCATION WHERE YOU TEACH:** _____
AGE OF THE STUDENTS YOU TEACH: _____ **NATURAL SCIENCES** **SOCIAL SCIENCES**

QUESTION	ESCALE			
	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
1. The fresh water on Earth is insufficient				
2. Water scarcity is due to water imbalance, as some areas are very wet, while others have very little water				
3. Freshwater is not scarce. There is enough for the Earth's inhabitants				
4. Water scarcity lies in the quality of available water due to pollution and degradation of the natural environment				
5. Large-scale hydraulic infrastructure (reservoirs, desalination plants, dams) enable us to get more water				
6. There are areas suffering from land degradation due to aridity, drought or human-generated erosion, which require water to be brought in from other areas that have more water resources				
7. In areas suffering from land degradation due to aridity, drought or erosion, it is necessary to implement technologies and economic activities adapted to the available water				
8. The main problems affecting water in Colombia are:	a. Scarcity			
	b. Poor management of water supplied			
	c. Dumping of waste waters without treatment			
	d. Poor water quality			
	e. Environmental degradation			
9. The main problems affecting water in the most remote regions of the country, such as the Alta Guajira are:	a. Scarcity			
	b. Poor management of water supplied			
	c. Dumping of waste waters without treatment			
	d. Poor water quality			
	e. Environmental degradation			
10. The water problem should be solved by	a. National Government			
	b. District/Departmental Government			
	c. The citizens			
11. Industrial facilities used to obtain more water damage the environment				
12. With climate change, water resources will become increasingly scarce				

QUESTION		ESCALE			
		Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
13. When I am in locations without water problems, I don't mind wasting water because it won't affect the environment					
14. The following solutions that are often used to get the water we consume are harmful to the environment:	a. Transferring water from one river to another, through man-made channels				
	b. Dam building				
	c. Reservoir construction				
	d. Buildings that remove salt from seawater to turn it into drinking water				
	e. Construction of independent rainwater collection systems				
15. If you were a water manager in Colombia, you would opt for:	a. More reservoirs to ensure supply				
	b. Transferring water from one river to another, through man-made channels, to ensure its supply				
	c. Controlling water demand and applying stringent costs to those that consume the most				
	d. Raising citizen awareness to reduce personal, family and professional consumption				
	e. Reducing leakage in the water networks				
	f. Reusing treated water after removal of human discharged pollutants				
16. If you were responsible for water management in the most remote regions of the country, such as the Alta Guajira, you would opt for:	a. Building a desalination plant to remove salt from seawater and turn it into drinking water				
	b. Encouraging water saving				
	c. Extracting more water from wells				
	d. Building more reservoirs				
	e. Reducing leakage in the water networks				
	f. Reusing treated water after removal of human discharged pollutants				
17. The water I use at home comes from:	a. Wells				
	b. The moorlands				
	c. Directly from rain				
18. The water we have used goes to:	a. Directly to wetlands				
	b. As a whole to streams and rivers				
	c. Irrigation water, after treatment				
	d. As drinking water, after treatment				
19. Water is treated before reaching my home					
20. The water that comes from my home must receive treatment					
21. Water consumption in Bogotá in strata 4, 5 and 6 is much higher than in strata 1, 2 and 3					

QUESTION	ESCALE			
	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
22. Given the amount of water on Earth, I don't think it is important to save water				
23. In Colombia we must save water				
24. In Bogotá we must save water				
25. We could save water in homes by:	a. Turning off the tap when brushing my teeth or soaping			
	b. Using low water consumption toilets			
	c. Consuming foods of mainly vegetable origin			
	d. Reusing shower water for the toilet			
	e. Buying fewer clothes			
	f. Consuming less meat			
26. In our urban environment we could save water by:	a. Adapting crop types to water availability			
	b. Adapting ornamental plants to water availability			
	c. Building independent rainwater collection systems			
	d. Increasing the production of necessary products instead of importing them			
	e. Doing away with golf courses			
	f. Eliminating private swimming pools			
27. The following actions affect water availability:	a. Buying a lot of clothing			
	b. Frequently changing smartphone, Tablet, computer...			
	c. Using plastic bags			
	d. Cutting down many trees			